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Design and Conversion of a BLDC Motor to a Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the conversion of a conventional Brushless DC (BLDC) motor into a Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor (VRSM) aimed at reducing reliance on rare-earth permanent magnets while lowering manufacturing cost and improving robustness. The proposed approach is particularly suited for electric vehicle (EV) and industrial drive applications where reliability and ease of maintenance are critical. The conversion process involves redesigning the stator and rotor geometry, performing detailed winding calculations, and fabricating the motor using laminated silicon steel. Electromagnetic performance, including flux distribution, torque characteristics, and thermal behavior, was evaluated using ANSYS Maxwell and RMXprt. A dedicated drive system was developed employing an Arduino Uno micro-controller and IR2110 gate drive integrated circuits to achieve appropriate phase excitation, sequential switching, and speed control. The experimental validation of the prototype confirmed that the design performed reliably under standard operating conditions. These results demonstrate that the proposed VRSM is a fully functional and effective alternative to conventional BLDC motors. By eliminating the need for rare-earth materials, it provides a dependable, low-cost solution perfectly suited for light electric vehicles and industrial applications.

Keywords:- BLDC motor, variable reluctance motor, motor conversion, electric vehicle

INTRODUCTION

The electric vehicle (EV) industry widely relies on Brush-less DC (BLDC) motors and Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs), both of which utilize rare-earth permanent magnets. Although these motors offer high efficiency and high torque density, their dependence on expensive and limited rare-earth materials raises significant concerns regarding cost and supply chain sustainability. As a result, there is a growing interest in Switched Reluctance Machines (SRMs) and Variable Reluctance Stepper Motors (VRSMs).

VRSMs operate based on the principle of reluctance torque and do not require permanent magnets; torque is produced by the tendency of the salient-pole rotor to align with positions of minimum magnetic reluctance. The research landscape for these machines has been shaped by several key studies: First, Fairall et al. [1] provided a comprehensive review of high-speed SRMs, highlighting them as high-value alternatives due to their low cost and ability to operate at speeds exceeding 20,000 RPM.

Following this, Sezen et al. [2] focused on the finite element modeling and control of high-power SRMs for hybrid vehicles, emphasizing the importance of precise magnetization curves for accurate simulation. Chiba and Kiyota [3] further reviewed the development of SRMs in the hybrid vehicle sector, demonstrates that these machines can achieve torque densities competitive with rare-earth

Machine Specifications and Pole Geometry

The required electromagnetic torque T_{req} is determined by the rated power P_{kw} and operating speed N :

$$T_{req} = \frac{P_{kw} \times 745.6}{2\pi(N/60)} \quad (1)$$

permanent magnet generators.

In terms of design and optimization, Li et al. [4] explored various modeling techniques and applications, suggesting that advanced optimization frameworks are essential for balancing efficiency and torque ripple. More recently, Bienkowski et al.[5] developed and validated an analytical model specifically for 8/6 and 10/8 SRMs, providing a critical tool for assessing electromagnetic torque. Finally, the foundational modeling and optimal control strategies for variable reluctance motors were established by Stepien and Bernat [6], who utilized numerical techniques to minimize power losses in stator windings.

This paper focuses on the conversion of an existing BLDC motor into an 8/6 VRSM by modifying the stator and rotor geometry while reusing the original motor housing. The primary objectives include eliminating rare-earth materials, designing and fabricating an 8/6 VRSM, implementing a microcontroller-based drive circuit, and evaluating electromagnetic and performance characteristics through simulation and experimental validation.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The design of the 8/6 Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor (VRSM) involves optimizing pole geometry and magnetic properties to adapt an existing BLDC frame. The 8/6 configuration was selected to balance structural simplicity with reduced torque ripple and smoother electromagnetic performance.

For effective torque production, stator (β_s) and rotor (β_r) pole arc angles must satisfy $\beta_s < \beta_r$ and $\beta_s + \beta_r < 2\pi/N_r$. The stroke angle is defined as:

$$\text{Stroke Angle} = \frac{2\pi}{N_s (Nr/2)} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1: Stator and rotor pole arc definitions.

Stator and Rotor Sizing

Stator dimensions are derived from the peripheral length and air-gap g . Key parameters include the outer diameter D_0 , stator pole area A_s , and yoke flux Φ_y :

$$D_0 = \frac{\text{Periphery}}{\pi}, \quad D = \frac{D_0}{2} + 49 \quad (3)$$

$$A_s = \left(\frac{D}{2} - g\right) L\beta_s, \quad \Phi = B_s A_s, \quad \Phi_y = \frac{\Phi}{2} \quad (4)$$

The stator height H_s is calculated by $H_s = \frac{D}{2} - g - \frac{D_{sh}}{2} - \frac{A_{sc}}{L}$.

Fig. 2: Stator geometry and dimensions.

Rotor parameters are determined to ensure magnetic saturation limits are respected:

$$A_r = \frac{D}{2}L\beta_r, \quad h_r = \frac{D_0}{2} - \frac{A_r}{L} - \frac{D}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$B_g = \frac{A_s B_s}{A_g}, \quad \text{where } A_g = \left(\frac{D-g}{2}\right) \frac{(\beta_r + \beta_s)\pi}{360} L \quad (6)$$

Winding Design and Material Selection

The turns per phase T_{ph} are derived from the peak current I_p and total MMF S , which accounts for magnetic intensities H across the core and air gap:

$$T_{ph} = \frac{S}{I_p}, \quad S = 2 \sum (H_k I_k) + \frac{H_{sc} I_{sc}}{2}$$

Design choices include laminated silicon steel for the core to minimize eddy currents, 22 SWG copper wire, and a reused BLDC housing to reduce costs. Final validation was performed via electromagnetic simulations to ensure flux efficiency and thermal stability.

Fig. 3: Rotor geometry and dimensions.

MODELLING AND SIMULATION

To validate the proposed Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor (VRSM) design prior to fabrication, a comprehensive electromagnetic transient analysis was conducted using ANSYS RMxprt and Maxwell 2D. The simulation utilized

geometric and material parameters derived from analytical calculations and AutoCAD schematics including stator/rotor dimensions, air gaps, and winding details to compute critical performance metrics such as inductance, magnetic flux density (B), and field intensity (H).

Fig. 4: Magnetic flux density (B) vector distribution during Phase B excitation.

The resulting field overlays, as illustrated in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, demonstrate the magnetic behavior when Phase B is energized. The flux vectors transition effectively through the rotor to the Phase B poles, completing the circuit through the stator yoke with maximum density concentrated at the active poles (indicated by green and yellow regions) while inactive poles remain in the blue region.

The simulation confirmed that the magnetic circuit operates as intended, with smooth flux linkage and torque waveforms indicating minimal leakage or saturation.

This pre-fabrication verification of stepwise rotor motion ensures the design's functional reliability and significantly reduces the need for iterative hardware development.

Fig. 5: Field intensity and flux line paths across the stator and rotor core.

Fabrication of the 8/6 VRSM

The fabrication of the 8/6 VRSM utilized a sustainable approach by repurposing the laminated silicon steel core and frame of a conventional BLDC motor, modified to accommodate eight salient stator poles. Each pole was wound with 100 turns of 22 SWG enameled copper wire a configuration selected through empirical

trials to optimize the balance between ampere-turns and thermal dissipation and subsequently coated with electrical varnish for insulation. To ensure mechanical stability and precise magnetic alignment, custom galvanized iron (GI) U-brackets were designed in AutoCAD and machined to secure the stator within the existing housing.

The corresponding six-pole rotor was fabricated from a solid mild steel cylindrical blank using precision lathe machining. The rotor geometry, shown in

Figure 9(a), was derived from the stator's physical constraints to maintain a uniform air gap and minimize torque ripple. Figure 9(b) shows the 8/6 VRSM setup.

Fig. 6: Six-pole rotor design and fabricated mild steel rotor component.

This integrated assembly, verified through AutoCAD modeling for dimensional accuracy and dynamic balance, ensures reliable stepwise motion while minimizing vibration and acoustic noise during operation.

VRSM ELECTRONIC DRIVE ARCHITECTURE

A dedicated electronic drive is required for the Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor (VRSM) to facilitate precise sequential phase excitation. The developed drive system integrates a microcontroller-based

control stage with a high-current power electronic switching stage. Figure 10 shows the driving circuit. The control logic is implemented using an Arduino Uno (ATmega328P), which generates the pulse-width modulated (PWM) signals required for phase commutation.

To interface the low-power logic with the high-power switching stage, an IR2110 high-and-low-side gate driver IC is utilized. Figure 11 shows the fabricated VRSM connected to the drive.

Fig. 7: U-Bracket assembly.

Fig. 8: IR2110 Gate Driver Configuration.

The IR2110 provides essential level-shifting for the high-side switch and independent control of the power MOSFETs. To ensure reliable high-side gate voltage, a bootstrap circuit comprising $10\mu\text{F}$ and $22\mu\text{F}$ capacitors is employed. This configuration enables fast switching transitions, thereby minimizing switching losses and ensuring electrical isolation between the control and power domains.

Power Switching and Protection

The power stage utilizes IRFB4110 N-

channel MOSFETs, selected for their high current handling capability (180A) and low $R_{DS(on)}$. These devices control the energization of inductive VRSM windings.

To protect the switching elements from inductive kickback, 1N4007 and 6A10 freewheeling diodes are integrated as fly back protection. Thermal stability is maintained via HS 49 heat sinks, ensuring the MOSFETs operate within safe junction temperature limits during continuous operation.

(a) (b)
Fig. 9: Rotor (a) and stator(b) of the fabricated VRSM.

Fig. 10: Complete Schematic of the VRSM Drive Circuit.

Fig. 11: Fabricated VRSM and drive.

System Integration and Specifications

The drive system was prototyped on a custom-designed PCB using Altium Designer, as detailed in Table 2. A 20V DC supply powers the motor phases, while regulated 15V and 5V rails support the

driver IC and microcontroller, respectively.

The resulting drive is a modular, low-cost solution capable of providing the high-speed switching necessary for electric mobility and robotic applications.

Table 1: Drive System Component Specifications

Component	Specifications
Microcontroller	Arduino Uno (CP2102)
Gate Driver	IR2110 High/Low Side Driver
Power MOSFETs	IRFB4110 (100V, 180A, $R_{DS(on)} = 4.5m\Omega$)
Diodes	1N4007 (Signal), 6A10 (Power Flyback)
Filter Capacitors	1000 μ F/25V, 100 μ F, 22 μ F
Thermal Mgmt.	HS 49 Heat Sinks (16 \times 12 \times 20 mm)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE

Analysis

The performance of the developed 8/6 VRSM was validated through a combination of finite element analysis (FEA) and hardware experimentation. The prototype demonstrated robust operational characteristics, with a high degree of correlation between simulated waveforms and experimental oscilloscope readings.

Steady-State Performance

The motor achieved a rated output torque of 1.2 Nm at a base speed of 1000 RPM. The efficiency exceeded 80% under rated conditions, demonstrating the effectiveness of the optimized pole geometry and the use of laminated silicon steel to minimize core losses. The key performance parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Measured Performance Parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Operating Voltage	V	12.0 V
Rated Phase Current	I	3.5 A
Output Torque	T_{out}	1.2 Nm
Operating Speed	N	1000 RPM
System Efficiency	η	> 80%

Electromagnetic Waveform Analysis

- Terminal Voltage Characteristics:** The terminal voltage V was monitored to evaluate the response of the asymmetric bridge converter under load. As shown in Fig. 12, the voltage profile remains stable, ensuring consistent flux growth during the excitation period.
- Phase Current and Torque Correlation:** The phase current I was measured using a Hall-effect sensor. The current waveform (Fig. 13) illustrates the inductive rise and decay characteristic of the variable reluctance

motor. This current profile is directly proportional to the instantaneous torque production, confirming that the driver successfully manages the back-EMF at rated speeds.

- Speed Characteristics:** Rotational speed N was verified using a digital tachometer. The linearity between the pulse frequency from the Arduino-based controller and the mechanical RPM (Fig. 14) confirms the precision of the timing logic in the developed drive system.

Fig. 12: Motor terminal voltage waveform during phase excitation.

Fig. 13: Measured phase current reflecting load-dependent excitation.

CONCLUSION

This research successfully demonstrated the feasibility of converting a conventional BLDC motor frame into an 8/6 Variable Reluctance Stepper Motor (VRSM). By utilizing a rare-earth-free design and optimizing rotor-stator geometry, a cost-effective alternative for electric vehicle and industrial automation applications was achieved. Experimental validation confirmed that the motor delivers significant torque density and efficiency exceeding 80%, validated through both ANSYS- based simulations and hardware

testing. The integration of an Arduino-based control system with IR2110 gate drivers proved to be a reliable and modular solution for phase switching.

This work highlights the scalability of VRSMs in low-maintenance, high-reliability systems. Future research will focus on the implementation of advanced control algorithms to minimize torque ripple and the development of sensor less position estimation techniques to further enhance system robustness.

Fig. 14: Motor speed profile under varying load conditions.

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